

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Community empowerment and creative economy

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Abstract

Community empowerment is related to efforts to increase the capacity and ability of marginalized communities in development. This empowerment concept is closely related to the creative economy. This research seeks to examine the extent to which the concept of community empowerment is linked to the concept of creative economy. The results show that previous research often links the concept of empowerment with the creative economy. Both are linear in concept definition and practice in the field.

Keywords: Community Empowerment; Creative Economy; Creative Industry; Development; Capacity

1. Introduction

Community empowerment is an effort to push people from powerless to powerful. The community is encouraged to have the ability to participate in development. Rakib & Syam (2016) wrote that this community empowerment is an effort made to encourage the community to have the opportunity to determine their own life goals and the organization that oversees them.

Efforts to encourage communities in improving the creative economy are often carried out with a community empowerment approach. Empowerment is an effort to encourage community capacity through motivating and fostering community awareness in developing their potential (Zubaedi, 2013). The concept of community empowerment is in line with the concept of creative economy. Purnomo (2016) writes that the concept of creative economy is related to the concept of creativity-based capital, where people are encouraged to utilize their potential in order to increase community economic growth in an area. Starting from here, the concepts of community empowerment and creative economy are interesting to study more deeply. This paper analyzes these two big concepts, so it is hoped that it can be useful for readers in understanding the relationship between the concept of community empowerment and the concept of creative economy.

2. Material and methods

This research uses document study as a data collection method. Sugiyono (2009) wrote that document studies can be used in the qualitative research process. This research uses secondary data, which is a data source that indirectly provides data to researchers as data collectors. Secondary data here is obtained through documents, archives, literature, and library materials.

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3. Result and discussion

3.1. Community Empowerment

Payne (Masrukin, et al, 2014) writes that empowerment is an effort to help people to have power in the decision-making process, which is influenced by social and personal factors. Furthermore, empowerment is related to efforts to foster ability and confidence in the use of strength from within and the environment. Crick (Azizy, 2003) defines community empowerment as an effort to create communities to actively participate in decision-making or public policy, where this participation is a requirement for the realization of democratic life.

Community empowerment is an effort to provide opportunities for people to actively participate in development. This effort is done through providing equal opportunities or rights in the political and policy decision-making process (Mardikanto & Soebianto, 2015). In line with this, Swift and Levin (Mardikanto, 2010) wrote that community empowerment is an effort to encourage the ability of marginalized, vulnerable, and weak communities to have access to productive resources. This is done by encouraging them to participate in development, as well as decisions that affect them.

Kartasasmita (Andriyani, et al, 2017) writes that community empowerment is closely related to the efforts made in encouraging the improvement of the dignity of marginalized communities, so that they can escape the shackles of poverty and underdevelopment. The World Bank (Narayan, ed, 2002) writes that community empowerment is an expansion of the assets and abilities of marginalized and poor communities to increase their participation, improve their negotiation skills, and strengthen their influence and control, as well as the accountability of institutions that affect their lives.

Community empowerment is an increase in the capacity of groups or individuals in the process of making effective choices, where this process transforms these choices into desired actions and outcomes (Alsop, et al., 2006). In line with this, Sumodiningrat (2007) writes that community empowerment is an effort made to increase the capacity and independence of the community, which is an effort towards community independence. This community empowerment contains 3 (three) basic notions. First, efforts are made to create conditions that provide opportunities for the community to develop. Second, efforts to increase the capacity of the community to participate in development, which is encouraged through funding assistance, training, institutional development, and so on. Third, efforts to provide protection to marginalized and weak communities in order to avoid the negative impacts of unbalanced competition.

3.2. Creative Economy

The creative economy is a concept of intensifying information and creativity that relies on ideas and knowledge from Human Resources and their production factors (Hasanah, 2015). The concept of creative economy is close to the concept of creative industries. Ananda & Susilowati (2018) define the creative industry as an industry that emphasizes the skills, talents, and creativity possessed by each individual. Furthermore, Hartomo & Cahyadin (2013) wrote that there are several indicators that affect the sustainability of creative economy businesses, including: (1) Production; (2) Market and Marketing; (3) Management and Finance; (4) Government Policy; (5) Economic Conditions; (6) Environment; (7) Business Partnerships; and (8) Family.

The Ministry of Trade of the Republic of Indonesia (2007) defines the definition of creative industries as industries related to the utilization of creativity, skills, and talents of individuals in achieving prosperity through work that can encourage the achievement of prosperity. This is done through the utilization of creativity. On the other hand, Rakib, et al (2018) stated that the basic elements of this creative industry are creativity, skills, and talents which have the potential to achieve prosperity through intellectual work. Furthermore, Akhmad & Hidayat (2015) stated that there are 14 (fourteen) Creative Economy Sub-Sectors, namely: (1) Advertising; (2) Architecture; (3) Art Goods Market; (4) Crafts; (5) Design; (6) Fashion; (7) Video, Film, and Photography; (8) Interactive Games; (9) Performing Arts (Showbiz); (10) Publishing and Printing; (11) Computer and Software Services; (12) Television and Radio (Broadcasting); (13) Research and Development (R&D); and (14) Culinary.

3.3. Community Empowerment & Creative Economy

Community empowerment is organized to facilitate local communities in planning, decision-making, and managing their resources. It aims to give people the capacity to manage the resources that affect their lives. In the end, marginalized communities are expected to have economic, ecological, and social independence in a sustainable manner (Noor, 2011). Chambers (Alfitri, 2011) emphasizes that community empowerment is a concept in economic development, which involves social values. Community empowerment is a new paradigm in development, which

involves elements of people centered, participatory, empowering, and sustainable. Starting from here, it can be seen that the concept of community empowerment is close to the concept of creative economy, where both are related to efforts made by the government in encouraging the community through the utilization of their interests, talents, knowledge, and skills to achieve independence. The independence in this case is economic independence.

Several previous studies have examined the relationship between community empowerment and the creative economy. Sanuri (2020) through his research examines creative economic empowerment based on community local wisdom with an outcome mapping approach. The results of his research show that the need for participatory planning in identifying community needs, determining the right partners and stakeholders, well-directed program design, work plans directed at training and development, and changing partner behavior. On the other hand, Andriani, et al (2024) through their research examined the empowerment of creative economic actors by the Creative Economy Division of the Ciamis Regency Tourism Office in Patakaharja Village, Rancah District, Ciamis Regency. The results of his research show that there is a need for optimization in technical training and assistance to business actors, increasing access to marketing and capital, and strengthening product pricing policies and regulations related to the quality of business products.

Rakib & Syam (2016) through their research examined community empowerment through the Life Skills Program based on local potential to increase family productivity in Lero Village, Suppa District, Pirang Regency. The results of his research show that community participation in the empowerment program is quite adequate. In addition, the community has adequate knowledge and skills in making products. Furthermore, the results of this study show the formation of 3 (three) Small Business Groups. On the other hand, Yulitasari, et al (2023) through their research examined creative economic empowerment made from rattan and coconut shells. The results of their research show that creative economic empowerment can be an effective solution in improving the family economy in rural areas. The following are some previous studies conducted by combining these two broad concepts can be seen in Table 1:

Table 1 Community Empowerment & Creative Economy Research

No.	Research Title	Author	Year
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1.	Empowerment of Creative Economy Actors by the Creative Economy Division of the Ciamis Regency Tourism Office (Case Study in Patakaharja Village, Rancah District, Ciamis Regency)	Andriani, dkk	2024
2.	Rattan and Coconut Shell-based Creative Economy Empowerment	Yulitasari, dkk	2023
3.	Creative Economy Empowerment Based on Community Local Wisdom with Outcome Mapping Approach	Sanuri	2020
4.	Community Empowerment through Life Skills Program Based on Local Potential to Increase Family Productivity in Lero Village, Suppa Sub-district, Blond Regency.	Rakib & Syam.	2016

Sumber: Andriani, dkk (2024); Sanuri (2020); Rakib & Syam (2016).

These previous studies show that the concept of community empowerment and the concept of creative economy are often used in examining efforts made by the government in encouraging community empowerment. The concept of community empowerment is often used interchangeably with the concept of creative economy. This shows that these two concepts are in line in relation to efforts to encourage people to have the power to access various productive economic resources in their environment. Community empowerment through the creative economy is described through various economic activities based on community creativity. Conversely, these creative economic activities are organized in an effort to encourage community capacity to utilize their capacities and abilities in line with the concept of community empowerment.

4. Conclusion

Community empowerment and creative economy are often used in examining the government's efforts to improve the ability of communities in development, in this case economic development. The concept of community empowerment is often used together or interchangeably with the concept of creative economy. Previous studies often link the concept of empowerment with the creative economy. Both concepts are linear in concept definition and practice in the field.

Creative economy performance can be achieved by community empowerment efforts. Conversely, community empowerment efforts can also be carried out in the creative economy. These two concepts can strengthen each other.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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